

Employee's Work Attitude - Sulekha Organization

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:
Chithra, N. "Employee's
Work Attitude - Sulekha
Organization." *Shanlax
International Journal of
Commerce*, vol. 6,
no. S1, 2018, pp. 54–64.

DOI:
[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2532943](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2532943)

Introduction

Attitude is more significant than the past, than education, than money, than circumstances, than what people do or say. It is further important than appearance, giftedness or skill. - W.C. Fields.

Attitude

The term attitude remains referred to as an individual's predisposition towards an object, person, or group that influences his or her response to be positive or negative, favorable or unfavorable. In other words, attitude is a settled way of thinking or feeling about someone or something, typically one that is reflected in a person's behavior.

Definition of Attitude

According to Allport (1935) Attitude is " Mental states, developed through experience, which are always ready to exert an active influence on an individual's response to any conditions or circumstances to which the person has been directed."

Employee Attitude

Attitude describes the way, an employee feels inside. These are his feelings towards the organization, his co-workers and his position within the company. Each employee has assertiveness towards the environment- either good or bad. This attitude can also influence how he performs. Because attitude is an innermost feeling, an employee's bad attitude might persist hidden. But if he is not careful, his bad attitude might show in his actions.

An employee's attitude towards the job and the company had the greatest impact on loyalty towards the organization. It should be remembered that any employee is capable of doing their work; nothing can be achieved if the employees have negative approach or negative attitude towards their job.

Having the right attitude can help to be a successful employee at the work place and can also lead to move up. The attitudes of employees are those related to work especially, attitudes that influence how well employees perform.

To lead employees effectively, managers logically seek to cultivate the kinds of attitudes that are associated with high performance. Two attitudes that might relate to high performance are gratification with one's job then commitment to the organization.

No matter how efficient an employee is, if he or she doesn't have the right approach towards the job, the results will be on the negative side. Each employee thinks of many plans for his or her career and job in particular. Thus, the key to success begins with the realization that everything is a matter of attitude and thus having the right attitude can be very positive for the employee's career.

If you have the right attitude, you are in a position to accept every situation, the way it is and take on the challenge. Employees with the right kind of attitude can help to take the company to the next level.

Importance of Maintaining a Positive Attitude in the Work place

Every individual in the place of work likes to hear respect for a job well done. If an employee recognizes that someone has poured their heart and soul into a project, recognize that individual with positive praise. Numerous times in the workplace many individuals never seem to become perceived for their hard work and it can have a negative effect on trust a positive attitude. Simply by giving praise, it serves a dual purpose by giving the other individual positive feedback and it makes him feel good to see the positive effects of what an employee said. This is a device to help maintain optimistic attitudes in the workplace.

Attitude is a vital factor in the work environment. Constructive attitudes can affect efficiency and enhance the work relationships between colleagues. If an employee wants to work in an environment where there are motivated and empowered employees, then individuals need to maintain positive healthy attitude.

The path to that type environment requires individuals that are willing to enforce positive attitudes. Negativity is critical and can grounds an organization to fail to meet its goals.

In the current scenario, the actual challenge in a workplace is to handle and overcome the hindrances and learn from hard and threatening experiences. The problems can be tackled by a person only with positive attitude, with the focused mind, and with efforts to overcome obstacles. A person with positive attitude can effortlessly survive in many tough conditions of life.

When a boss or superior comes to a person and asks for some work to be done, and if the response from employees is "I don't think that I can organize this" or "What happens if I fail?" shows negative attitude of a person and superior may keep the person away and pay no attention to him in further projects. But if the person replies in positive way like "I will definitely put my total efforts and get work completed by the finale of the day", then the boss will consider him as earnest persons. The person with constructive attitude will become a role of inspiration to others. Developing positive attitude helps in overwhelming stress, escalations self-esteem, self-confidence, and makes an individual more creative or dynamic. There are many benefits of positive attitude at place of work.

Creates a Positive Environment

In general, employers put effort to mark their employees pleased, keep their values high and struggle to create a positive atmosphere for them to work so that they can understanding the benefits of higher efficiency and as a result, higher profitability can be achieved. Disputes at work place should not be treated as problems, they should be considered as encounters. This helps in generating positive environment and gives benefits to both employees and employers. Constantly try to contemplate on how you can make something stress-free or more gratifying. A positive approach in setting goals and in overcoming challenges by leader makes other colleagues to include positive attitude. A positive attitude is catchier.

Helps to Achieve Goals

Persuading customers is much easier for a person with positive attitude. Research has also confirmed that sales promotional that think positively and trust in the benefits of their product have improved sales performance. If a person has positive attitude about attaining goals and accomplishment, they are more inclined to take action in order to achieve it. Progressive thinking is noticeable in an achiever. Positive intellectual with stimulus helps in attainment different goals. It earns more benefits even after goal is achieved.

Increase Productivity Levels

Negative attitude cause a mean cycle that deteriorates productivity. A positive attitude can be achieved by improving relationships with colleagues in positive way and remembering the jobs “good side”. By reconsidering the “virtuous side” of a job, it is possible to reinforce passion in it, which results in increase in production. Modification of perception or thinking about something more positive can eliminate stressful spirits. If stress is condensed among the employees, then improved health can be attained as stress can have a severe adverse impact on health. These consequences in less tasteless days and improved productivity.

Positive Attitude and Team Building

Numerous business leaders have an impress that promoting and inspiring positive thinking in the workplace will help in team building. If ideas of member are encouraged and a positive attitude is taken up, team members will get along with one another more frequently, leading to fewer conflicts. At workplace, if a person is not positive, co-workers will not be interested to be around him. Hence, if a person has positive attitude to work and others from place to place, then co-workers can sense that is a enjoyable person to be around.

A ‘ Can do’ in oneself illustrates positive attitude and has an influence in the work too. Being positive makes a person stronger, contented, and in good health. The power of positive thinking is crucial for happiness in life and a successful career Employee will love his work more and achieve his goals at workplace more easily and faster with positive attitude.

Factors Influencing Positive Attitude towards their Work

Workers pay attention to several features of their work environment, including:

- Features of the job (a purpose of Organizing activities.)
- How they are treated(related to Management actions)
- The interactions they form with social group and managers(also Leadership related)
- The level of stress the job entails.

Work Related Attitude

A being can have thousands of attitudes, but Managerial Behaviour focuses our consideration on a very limited number of works -related attitudes. These work related attitude tap positive or negative evaluations that employees hold about aspects of their work environment. Utmost of the research in Organizational Behaviour has been concerned with three attitudes

- Job Satisfaction
- Job Involvement and
- Organisational commitment

Job Satisfaction

The term job satisfaction to a person's overall attitude to his or her job. A person with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive attitudes about their job, while a person who is dissatisfied with his or her job holds negative attitudes about the job. When individuals speak of worker attitudes, more often mean job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is how worked an individual is with his or her job. Scholars and Human Resources professionals generally make a distinction between affective job satisfaction and cognitive job satisfaction. Affective job satisfaction is the extent of pleasurable emotional feelings individuals, have about their jobs overall, and is different to cognitive job satisfaction which is the extent of individuals satisfaction with particular facets of their jobs, such as pays, pension arrangement, working hours and numerous other aspects of their jobs. Job facet gratification refers to state of mind about exact job aspects, such as salary, benefits and relationships with co-workers.

Satisfaction with Work

The emotive state of a worker while working is life-threatening to job attitudes. Although a person may self-identify in terms of profession, for example: as a doctor, lawyer or engineer, it is their well-being at work is significant in characterizing job attitude. Satisfaction with work can be analysed by evaluation (I like or dislike my job) , cognitively (My work is challenging) and behaviourally (I am reliable)

Supervision

Supervision as a significant relationship with productivity. Though, Management can only be taken positively with recognition. Consequently, it is significant to confirm a positive attitude to work.

Co- Workers

Co-workers are the common source of job stress, as demonstrated by studies using Role Theory.

Pay and Promotion

Particular employee obligation and organizational behaviour coordination, compensation and progression function as positive strengthening, demonstrating that the worker is valued and reinforcing loyalty.

Job Involvement

The term Job involvement is a more recent addition to the OB Literature while their isn't complete agreement what the term means. A workable definition states that job involvement measures the degree to which a person identifies him with his or her job and considered his or her perceived performance level important to self- worth. Employees with a high level of job involvement strongly identify with and really care. About the kind of the work they do.

Organizational Commitment is the emotional attachment people have towards the company they work for. In other words, organizational commitment refers to an employee's loyalty to and engagement with the organization. A highly committed employee is one who accepts and believes the company's values, is willing to put out effort to meet the company's goals, and as a strong desire to remain with the company. People who are committed to their company often refers to their company as "We" as opposed to "They" as "In this company, we have great benefits". The way we refer to the company shows the type of affection and identification we have with the company.

Review of Literature

Literature Survey

From the Wall Street Journal Online

A majority of U.S. Employees say they are satisfied with their job and nearly half pride in their career, according to a recent. “Harris Interactive Poll”. Still, many U.S. workers dislike their jobs, grieve from Burnout and don’t have good feelings about their employers and senior managers, the poll shows. Employees in small organizations are most likely to have positive attitude towards their jobs, their employees and their top managers.

Of people working for small employers, 54% of those polled say they are satisfied with their job, and company 38% of those working for large employers feel they are at dead-end jobs, compared with 24% of those salaried for companies feel “this remains the best organizational to work for” only 25% of the people working for large organizations, compared through for insignificant employers, believe that the top manages display integrity and morality. This survey also displays that younger workers have much more undesirable view of their job than older workers. Amongst the older workers, 59% say a good arrangement of their pride comes from their work and careers, compared with just 37% of the younger workers. Similarly, among 64% of the older workers, only 47% of the younger workers truly care about the fortune of the organization for which they work. Generally, while 59% of the employees are gratified with their jobs, that two out of every five 41% of the workers aren’t satisfied. In addition, one-third of the workforces feel they are leading-edge dead-end occupations, and “trying to cope with feeling of burn out”. Burn out is much more predominant among the workers ages between 18-24 years, 47% report feeling burned out, compared with 28% of the older workers.

Ganguli (1964) has argued that the factors that determine performance of the workers in an industrial job can be classified under three heads:

1. Personal factors
2. Work factors
3. Environmental (physical and social) factors.

Personal Factors refers to skills of workers and the degree of motivation that determine the extent to which he will apply his skill to the job. Work influence refers to tools and equipment, technique of work and materials used. Instances of environmental factors are (a) physical lighting, ventilation, etc. (b) societal and emotional nature of leadership (supervisory and managerial), social climate in the shop, nature of the group formation amongst members, etc. and (c) Environment of organizational controls, communication patterns, etc.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the employees attitude towards their job.
- To find out the association between the level of satisfaction and employees perception of their job.

Hypothesis

There is No Association between Marital Status and Level of Satisfaction

There is no Association between Incentives and Level of Satisfaction Company Profile

Sulekha vision is to be the home-screen icon for local services for 100 million Indians every day. Sulekha unites 25 million users with 5 million businesses each month across different local service categories each month – including home services, coaching & tuition, property, rentals, computer training and 500+ other sub-categories. Sulekha helps users to minimize the time in finding the right service provider, to reduce the cost of the service and to minimize the hassle of dealing with

service providers. For service associates, Sulekha eases the time & money involved in ruling a customer and minimizes the hassle of closing a sale. Sulekha attains this by increasing liquidity (number of users and service partners), increasing quality (genuine users, high quality businesses) and increasing speed of getting the job done.

Need for the Study

Utmost individuals spend a majority of their time at work. Dealing with the challenges and conflict becomes much more difficult without a good attitude. The effects of having a positive attitude are significant and create environment where people can collaborate and work together to get their jobs done.

If individuals maintain a positive and optimistic attitude, it attracts people to work together and can help everyone get through conflict and stressful situations in the workplace. Learning to focus on the positive side of their job and discouraging individuals to stay away from the negative side of the workplace is a motivating factor to keep going until their task are completed.

Whenever an employee encounters obstacles, their attitude influences how they will handle the obstacles. If they have a positive attitude they will be more determined to work through the difficulties and get the job done. Negative attitude can stall their progress and make it next to impossible to work through the obstacles effectively. Having a right attitude towards their work can increase the productivity.

Sulekha is a huge and varied fastness of technologies, companies, services and politics that is truly global in nature. Sulekha has gone through many phases of growth and diversification. It is the place where customers have more contact with the employees. Hence, positive attitude towards the employee's job can help people get a better response from the employee's side.

This study aims to find whether there is any association between the satisfaction level and their perception towards their job.

Further this study is conducted to find whether the employees working in Sulekha industry are having a positive attitude towards their job.

Sampling Design

In this project, the samples have been collected from the population using simple random sampling technique.

Sample Size

The sample size of the study is 100. The questionnaire consists of 25 questions.

Limitations of the Study

- The area of data collection has been restricted to Chennai City only.
- The study is purely based on the data collected through questionnaire.
- The sample size is restricted to 100.
- The suggestions are based on finding of the present study.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The procedure of analysis is essential to interpret the result obtained and to draw up inference in order to have a meaning for the study. Each question from the questionnaire, which is the source of primary data collected, is converted in the form of the table. The table describes the percentage of data collected and the percentage of data, which falls under a particular criticism, form the basis for drawing inference. The tools applied for the analysis are simple percentage method and the chi-square test.

Table 1
Frequency Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Good Place	100	3.00	5.00	4.7100	.53739	-1.706	.241	2.063	.478
Comfortable Work	100	3.00	5.00	4.5400	.59323	-.898	.241	-.162	.478
Equally and Fairly	100	1.00	5.00	4.3300	.94340	-1.373	.241	1.241	.478
Performance Appraisal	100	1.00	5.00	4.2500	1.08595	-1.434	.241	1.205	.478
Abilities & Skills	100	1.00	5.00	4.2400	.93333	-1.033	.241	-.415	.478
Responsibilities	100	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.84087	-.499	.241	-1.116	.478
Promotion Policies	100	2.00	5.00	4.1700	.79207	-.564	.241	-.459	.478
Working Holidays	100	1.00	5.00	3.1200	1.22499	-1.033	.241	-.766	.478
Valid N (listwise)	100								

Interpretation

It is found from the study that employees have a positive attitude towards the work. They feel that the organization is a good place to work which is proven by the highest mean (4.71). Employees also feel that the organization has a comfortable work place where their abilities and skills are best utilized performance appraisal has the least mean (4.252) towards work attitude.

Table 2
Association between Marital Status and Level of Satisfaction

			Level of satisfaction			Total
			Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	
Marital Status	Married	Count	36 _a	20 _b	0 _{a,b}	56
		% within Level of satisfaction	70.6%	42.6%	.0%	56.0%
	Un Married	Count	15 _a	27 _b	2 _{a,b}	44
			29.4%	57.4%	100.0%	44.0%
Total		Count	51	47	2	100
		% within Level of satisfaction	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Each subscript letter denotes a subset of Level of satisfaction categories whose column proportions do not differ significantly from each other at the .05 level.

H0- There is no significant relationship between marital status and level of satisfaction.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.399 ^a	2	.006
Likelihood Ratio	11.285	2	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	10.155	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5.
The minimum expected count is .88.

Interpretation

The Pearson chi-square test of the table is 0.006, which is greater than the significant value 0.005 therefore there is no significant relationship between marital status and level of satisfaction.

Association between Incentives and Level of Satisfaction

			Level of satisfaction			Total
			Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	
Incentives	Highly Satisfied	Count	40 _a	16 _b	0 _b	56
		% within Level of satisfaction	78.4%	34.0%	.0%	56.0%
	Satisfied	Count	5 _a	23 _b	1 _{a,b}	29
		% within Level of satisfaction	9.8%	48.9%	50.0%	29.0%
	No Opinion	Count	4 _a	6 _a	1 _a	11
		% within Level of satisfaction	7.8%	12.8%	50.0%	11.0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	2 _a	2 _a	0 _a	4
			3.9%	4.3%	.0%	4.0%
Total		Count	51	47	2	100
		% within Level of satisfaction	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Ho : There is no significant relationship between incentives and level of satisfaction

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	26.424a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	27.612	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	10.895	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	100		

Interpretation

The Pearson chi-square test of the table is 0.00, which is lesser than the significant value 0.005 therefore there is significant relationship between job perceive and level of satisfaction.

Summary

The study is on the theme “Employees work attitude towards their organization”. Attitude refers to as an individual’s predisposition towards an object, person, or group that influences his or her response to be positive or negative, favorable or unfavorable.

The main objectives of the study are to study the employees work attitude towards their organization and to find out the association between the level of satisfaction and employees perception of their job.

The primary data collected from 100 respondents using questionnaire and secondary data also been collected from journals, books and magazines.

The analysis of data is conducted using simple percentage method, chi-square test, association and it is interpreted.

The major finding of the study is that most of the employees have a good attitude towards their job. Majority of the employees perceive their job as challenging, interesting and pleasurable. There is positive association between level of job satisfaction and employees perception. Employees work performance can excel if more incentives are provided.

Findings

Findings for the data collected are as follows:

Demographic

- Majority of the respondents (63%) are from the age group of 18-25
- Majority of the respondents (57%) are female category
- Majority of the respondents (71%) are graduates.
- Majority of the respondents (56%) are married.
- Majority of the respondents (48%) are belonging to the income level of between Rs.20001 - Rs.30000.
- Majority of the respondents (47%) of the respondents are software engineer.

Descriptive

- Majority of the respondents (48%) have work experience of 1 to 3 years.
- Majority of the respondents (40%) perceive their job as interesting
- Majority of the respondents(51%) are highly satisfied
- Majority of the respondents (18%) have a fair pay and other incentives in their job satisfaction factors of the company
- Majority of the respondents that (83%) of the respondents are satisfied with their present working hours
- Majority of the respondents (56%) are highly satisfied with the incentives and other benefits.
- Majority of the respondents that (81%) have said those incentives and other benefits increase a better work performance.
- Majority of the respondents that (75%) of them strongly agree that their organization is a good place to work.
- Majority of the respondents that (59%) have strongly agree for their comfortable work in their environment.
- Majority of the respondents that (52%) have strongly agree about the employees abilities and skills in the organization.

- Majority of the respondents that (58 %) have strongly agree about the company treats the employees equally and fairly.
- Majority of the respondents that (40%) have no opinion in working holidays
- Majority of the respondents that (41%) are satisfied with the promotion policies in the company
- Majority of the respondents that (46%) are highly satisfied with their responsibilities which given in the company.
- Majority of the respondents that (58%) are highly satisfied with their performance appraisal in their company.
- Majority of the respondents that (7%) has no opinion of recommending others.
- Majority of the respondents that (74%) needs a higher position to change a current job,.

Association

- There is no association between age and job satisfaction of satisfaction. (0.060%)
- There is no association between marital status and level of satisfaction (0.006%).
- There is an association between incentives and level of satisfaction. (0.000)

Suggestions

- It is found that employees will have a better work performance and have a good attitude if there is a fair pay. Some of the employees are not satisfied with their incentives. So it is suggested to provide a better pay and a salary hike.
- It is suggested that employees seeks rewarding system for better achievement.
- From the study, it is found that most of the employees are not satisfied with the promotion policies adopted in their organization. It is suggested that promotion policies can be made much simpler.
- It is suggested that employee's attitude can be improved by recognition and employee friendly approach.
- It is found that employees seek a fair performance appraisal, a good work life balance, healthy employer-employee relationship and recognition from management.
- Employees expect a flexible working hours and a feasible approach towards their management.
- Many employees look for good opportunities to develop their career. So opportunities for advancement can be made available.
- It is found that some employees seek a better training towards job and motivation.

Conclusion

From the study it has been observed that most of the employees perceive their job as challenging, interesting and pleasurable. There is a positive and a moderate association between level of satisfaction and how the employees perceive their job. Most of the employees have a positive attitude towards their job. But some of the employees feel that there will be a better work performance and have a positive attitude, if there is a better pay, incentives and other benefits. Beyond all, self-confidence and optimistic view can improve employees attitude towards their job.

References

- Adams, J.S. "Wage Inequities, Productivity and Work Quality", *Industrial Relations*, vol. 3, no. 1, 1963, pp. 9-16.
- Agarwal, J.C. *Theory and Principles of Education*, Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi, 1985.
- Aggarwal, K.G. *Supervisor-Man and Leader*, National Labour Institute, New Delhi, 1988.

Aggarwal, R.C. Constitutional Development and National Movement of India, 2009.

Akbar Hussain, N. Hasnain and Anisha Khan. "Occupational Stress and Life Satisfaction among High School Female Teachers", *Personality Study and Group Behaviour*, vol. 27, no. 28, 2007-2008, pp. 61-71.

Arvey, Richard D. et al. "Job Satisfaction: Environmental and Genetic Components", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 74, no. 2, 1989, pp. 187-192.

Cross Cultural Management, Armstrong, T.O. et al. *Social Problems*, Harper, New York, vol. 12, no. 2, 1971, pp. 69-84.